

WATER QUALITY OBJECTIVES FOR
THE GREAT LAKES

Andrew Robertson

Office of Marine Pollution Assessment, NOAA
Rockville, Maryland

Abstract

The United States and Canada signed the Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement in 1972 and renegotiated and strengthened it in 1978. In order to establish criteria for protection and against which to measure water quality status, the Agreement calls for the development of objectives for potentially polluting substances and effects. To develop these objectives, a set of guidelines were developed. The most important of these are: 1) the objectives are intended to protect all beneficial uses of the Great Lakes; 2) they are set at the level of no detectable effect; 3) uncertainties concerning their development are always resolved in favor of protection; 4) all objectives must be scientifically defensible; 5) they are not necessarily practical for direct implementation as regulatory standards; 6) they are not intended to protect all beneficial uses under any conditions; and 7) they are intended to be subject to periodic review. The development of these objectives is illustrated by two examples.

The United States and Canada share a major resource in their joint ownership of the five Great Lakes, four of which lie along the boundary between the two countries. These lakes contain approximately 20% of the world's surface liquid fresh water and are a major factor in the regional economy, being used for shipping, drinking water, hydroelectric power generation, cooling and makeup water for industry, commercial fishing, recreation, irrigation, and waste disposal.

By the late 1960s, it had become clear to the two countries that the water quality of this resource was deteriorating due to indiscriminate use, especially uncontrolled shoreline development and waste disposal. To reverse this trend they negotiated a water quality agreement for the Great Lakes that was signed in 1972. This agreement was revised and reaffirmed by the two governments in 1978. It expresses the determination of the United States and Canada to restore and enhance the water quality of the Great Lakes System. It has formed the basis of a binational pollution control program on the Lakes and has led to substantial improvements in, at least certain, aspects of water quality.

This agreement specifies general water quality objectives for the Great Lakes. These call for the Great Lakes to be:

- "a. Free from substances that directly or indirectly enter the waters as a result of human activity and that will settle to form putrescent or otherwise objectionable sludge deposits, or that will adversely affect aquatic life or waterfowl;
- "b. Free from floating materials such as debris, oil, scum, and other immiscible substances resulting from human activities in amounts that are unsightly or deleterious;
- "c. Free from materials and heat directly or indirectly entering the water as a result of human activity that alone, or in combination with other materials, will produce colour, odour, taste, or other conditions in such a degree as to interfere with beneficial uses;
- "d. Free from materials and heat directly or indirectly entering the water as a result of human activity that alone, or in combination with other materials, will produce conditions that are toxic or harmful to human, animal, or aquatic life; and
- "e. Free from nutrients directly or indirectly entering the waters as a result of human activity in amounts that create growths of aquatic life that interfere with beneficial uses."

Such objectives, while valuable in specifying the general status desired for the Great Lakes' waters, are too general to be used directly as the basis for a regulatory program. Thus, the Agreement goes further and attempts to detail more specific objectives. These are defined as, "...the concentration or quantity of a substance or level of effect that the Parties agree, after investigation, to recognize as a maximum or minimum desired limit for a defined body of water or portion thereof, taking into account the beneficial uses or level of environmental quality which the Parties desire to secure and protect."

When the Agreement was signed in 1972, it was not possible to state for most polluting substances or effects what the maximum or minimum level should be to protect the beneficial uses of the Great Lakes and even for those where levels were specified it was felt that careful consideration might well lead to improved values. Thus, the Agreement calls for a continuing effort to establish and revise objectives for polluting substances and effects in the Great Lakes. It then commits the countries to develop and carry out programs directed toward the achievement of these objectives.

The objectives thus provide the underpinning of the extensive program the United States and Canada have been carrying out to improve the quality of the Great Lakes. They form the basis for determinations of how much of what substances and effects can be allowed in the Lakes and what type and magnitude of remedial programs are needed.

This paper attempts to present a summary of the framework that has evolved for the development of these objectives and to illustrate the procedures in their development. I believe such information is valuable, not only to help explain the program being conducted to protect the Great Lakes, but also as an example for water quality programs elsewhere especially in the oceans. Recently there has been a strong push, including even a bill introduced in the U.S. Congress, for the determination of the "assimilative capacity" of marine waters for various pollutants. That is for determination of how much of specific pollutants a specified marine area can accept before unacceptable, or even detectable, impacts occur. The development of specific objectives for the Great Lakes is based on much the same idea. Thus, the experience in these waters may well prove useful in providing guidance for the development of programs directed toward controlling the deterioration of estuaries and other marine areas.

Guidelines for Development of Objectives

The Water Quality Agreement assigns the responsibility for developing recommendations for specific water quality objectives to the International Joint Commission (IJC), a binational body which provides advice and recommendations to the two countries on problems of mutual concern that arise along the U.S.-Canada boundary. To carry out this responsibility, the IJC established a committee composed of water quality experts to make recommendations concerning these objectives. When this group first met, it was found that there were divergent views and major uncertainties on a number of aspects of the basic philosophy to be used in developing these objectives. Thus, the first task of the group was to establish agreement on a general framework to guide the development of the objectives. Since that time the group has developed objectives for a large number of substances and effects, and the

framework has been tested and modifications made as required.

Through this process a number of general guidelines have been established. Although these have not been considered inviolate and they have been disregarded or modified when this seemed justified, they have proven very useful as general guides. They have led to the development of an internally consistent set of water quality objectives that have been largely adopted by the two countries. The more important and fundamental of these guidelines are presented in the following listing. To avoid complexity, these guidelines are presented based on the assumption that the objective for a toxic substance, such as a heavy metal or toxic organic pesticide, is being developed. Objectives for other types of substances as well as physical effects (e.g., temperature) and biological properties (e.g., levels of pathogens) have also been developed. Most of the guidelines apply in such cases, but certain rather obvious modifications have to be made in specific instances.

1. The objectives are intended to protect all beneficial uses of the Great Lakes. This means that the objective for each pollutant is set through a process of determining the levels at which the pollutant starts to interfere with the various uses of the water. The most sensitive of these is then designated as the use to be protected and the maximum (or less commonly minimum) level where that use is not interfered with is established as the objective for that pollutant. The aesthetic and recreational value of maintaining the ecosystems in the Great Lakes is considered a beneficial use and protection of this use through protection of aquatic life has been the most common basis for establishing the objectives. However, provision of a public water supply and, in a few cases, recreational activities have also been found to be the most sensitive use in specific instances. It can be noted that this approach could be easily altered to allow for protection of only certain selected uses for specified areas. Although this has not been done in the Great Lakes, it would obviously be quite possible, if one knows the levels required to protect the various uses in an area, to set the objective at a level to protect certain uses, but not the most sensitive ones. The decision on which uses to protect and which to sacrifice in a certain area is a decision to be made by the representatives of the people in our democratic system. In the Great Lakes case these representatives through the Water Quality Agreement and the IJC have specified the protection of all beneficial uses.

2. The objectives are set at the level of no detectable effect. Except where results of highly questionable validity are involved, the objectives are set at levels that are just beyond the limit where effects have been detected. This means that in the common situation where the most sensitive use is protection of aquatic life, the objective is not necessarily set at the level where mortality is first observed. In many cases more subtle sublethal effects such as metabolic or reproductive changes have been detected at lower levels of the pollutant. As the consequences of these changes in wild populations of organisms are very difficult to ascertain and may well be detrimental, the objectives are set at a no-effect level to assure that degradation does not occur.
3. Uncertainties concerning the development of the objectives are always resolved in favor of protection. The objectives are intended to be the level of a substance or effect where assurance can be given to water resource managers that all beneficial uses will be protected (see, however, guideline 6). Thus, in instances where uncertainties exist, these are resolved on the side of protection. For example, it is known that different forms of certain metals have quite different toxicities (e.g., Andrew 1976). Thus, it would be desirable to develop separate objectives for the various forms of these metals, based on the different levels of toxicity. However, so much uncertainty exists as to how to measure the different forms, what is the relative toxicity of these forms, and what are the rates of transformation from one form to another under various conditions in the environment that this approach has not been attempted. Instead the conservative approach of basing the objectives on concentrations of total metal and assuming these may be entirely in the most toxic form has been adopted. It is anticipated that future research may well resolve the uncertainties. When this happens the objectives will be revised and objectives for the various toxic forms developed as feasible.
4. All objectives must be scientifically defensible. The objectives are the considered opinion of scientific experts as to the levels that various pollutants can reach while still protecting all beneficial uses. Their development is based solely on scientific information available in the published literature. This is done to assure that the logic and process for development of the objectives can be traced and evaluated by other scientists. A rationale is attached to each objective explaining its development

and referencing the publications on which it is based. In cases where there is inadequate information in the literature to support the development of an objective for a pollutant no objective is developed pending the acquisition of more adequate results.

5. The objectives are not necessarily practical for direct implementation as regulatory standards. In certain cases objectives have been developed that specify levels of a pollutant that are so low that they are very difficult, if not impossible, to measure under the actual conditions in the Great Lakes. At other times objectives have been developed that specify levels that might cause major economic or societal disruptions (e.g., industrial closures) if enforced in specific areas. Such practical matters are obviously of overriding importance in specific instances. However, they have not been considered during the development of the objectives and fall outside the expertise of the committee members developing the objectives. It is certainly intended that these aspects be considered before the objectives are accepted as regulatory standards. However, it is felt very desirable to have the level needed to protect all beneficial uses determined on a purely scientific basis before adjustments are made to meet regulatory, economic, and political realities. In other words, the objectives are intended to be just what this word implies, goals for which we should strive, not necessarily the immediately attainable levels that should be permitted in the environment from a regulatory standpoint.
6. The objectives are not intended to protect all beneficial uses under any and all conditions, and their development and adoption does not preclude the need for other actions to protect these uses. The objectives have been developed to protect all beneficial uses from the effects of individual pollutants. However, the pollutants often enter the environment as part of complex mixtures and persist there as part of such mixtures. We know that the mixing of two or more pollutants often leads to synergistic or antagonistic effects on the toxicity of the individual substances. However, in almost all cases we do not know enough to predict the magnitude of these effects. It certainly cannot be assumed that if the levels of several individual pollutants are each kept within their objectives that the mixture will not have deleterious

impacts (Wong et al., 1978). Given the infinite possibilities for combinations, it may never be possible to study and predict the consequences of all combinations. Thus, the use of objectives also requires complementary monitoring programs to make certain that unforeseen degradation is not occurring. Further, the objectives are developed based on the assumption that the limnological conditions and ecosystems commonly found in the Great Lakes are present. In local situations within the Lakes and certainly in other bodies of water where quite different conditions, biological communities, and/or beneficial uses occur, the Great Lakes' objectives may not apply. Revised objectives taking these differences into account can, of course, be developed for these different situations.

7. The objectives are intended to be subject to periodic review with revisions as required. The objectives have been developed based on the best currently available information. As more studies are carried out and more is learned, it is expected that the present objectives will need to be revised. A program of periodically reexamining and, where necessary, redoing the objectives has been instituted.

Examples of Objective Development

Based on these guidelines, objectives have been developed for a large number of substances and effects. This has been done by assigning primary responsibility for each proposed objective to one or two individuals. These experts review the literature related to the toxicity and other aspects of the substance or effect under consideration and produce a draft objective with an accompanying rationale. This is then rigorously reviewed by the other members of the committee and in some cases also by outside experts. To illustrate the development of objectives, two examples are presented below--one for a relatively straightforward toxic material, zinc, and the other for a more complex example, the nutrient phosphorus.

Zinc

Zinc is found naturally in the Great Lakes at relatively low concentrations due to the weathering of rocks in the drainage basin. It is used in many industrial processes and products and is a byproduct of the burning of zinc-containing fossil fuels. Large-scale increases of human populations and industrial development have caused a recent increase in the concentrations of this metal in the Lakes.

An examination of the literature related to zinc toxicity shows that fish can be quite sensitive to the soluble form of this metal. In

laboratory studies using Lake Superior water, Brungs (1969) found reduced spawning of fathead minnows (*Pimephales promelas*) at 180 µg/l, but no effect at 30 µg/l. Also, in the laboratory Sprague et al. (1965) found juvenile salmon (*Salmo salar*) avoided levels as low as 54 µg/l. Out of all the studies that could be found dealing with zinc toxicity or other effects of zinc, these are the two in which sensitivity was detected at the lowest levels. Effects have been detected for fish in their natural habitat, but at somewhat higher levels. Existing evidence indicates that invertebrates are even less sensitive, while other uses of the Lakes were found to be much less sensitive. For example, the recommended level for zinc in drinking water in the United States is 5000 µg/l (National Academy of Science and National Academy of Engineering 1973). Thus, the committee judged the protection of aquatic life to be the most sensitive use and recommended an objective for this element in unfiltered Great Lakes' water of 30 µg/l, based on protection of such life especially fish. This one value has been judged adequate for application throughout the entire Great Lakes System. This was decided even though it is well known that zinc toxicity varies in relation to water hardness, pH, and other factors. Available evidence indicates that the variation in toxicity over the range of conditions in the Great Lakes is small enough that this one value will serve in all or almost all areas.

Phosphorus

Phosphorus presents a much more complex situation for developing an objective. The usual environmental concern with this element is not its toxicity, but the fact that it acts as a fertilizing or enriching substance, thus causing increased biological production. Although elemental phosphorus is quite toxic, this form is quickly oxidized and is practically never present in aquatic environments, with the minor exception of a few cases related to industrial accidents.

Phosphorus commonly occurs in water as the inorganic phosphate ion or as complexes of this ion with other ions or with organic matter. In the inorganic form, phosphorus is an essential nutrient for plant and animal growth. In fact in most situations in the Great Lakes, phosphorus is the nutrient in shortest supply relative to the amounts needed for algal growth. Thus, it is the usual limiting factor for primary production, the basic source of organic matter to support all the life in the Great Lakes.

Man's activities have greatly increased the amounts of phosphorus present in the Great Lakes. Especially sewage effluents, but also agricultural runoff, industrial waste disposal, and other activities, add large amounts of this element. This has led to increased biological production with associated undesirable changes, such as increased algal growths in boating and bathing areas, shifts to less desirable fish, and

increased instances of tastes and odors in drinking water (Beeton 1969, Schelske, and Stoermer 1972). The basic problem then is degraded water quality due to nutrient enrichment. An objective is needed to specify the permissible maximum level of phosphorus. (No attempt has been made to set a minimum level, although this would be needed if it is desired to assure that biological production stays at high enough levels to support all beneficial uses, e.g., sport and commercial fisheries).

Obviously the usual procedure of setting an objective at the no-effect level would not be useful in this situation. Phosphorus has a desirable effect, permitting biological production, but too much of the element and so too much production causes undesirable consequences. Here we need to set an objective that is the maximum allowable, while still maintaining the Lakes in the condition desired by the two countries.

One thing that was immediately obvious in dealing with phosphorus was that an objective containing one value that applied to all parts of the Lakes would not be satisfactory. Different parts of the Lakes naturally had and should continue to have different levels of phosphorus and so different biological properties. Thus, objectives were developed separately for Lakes Superior, Huron, Michigan, and Ontario and for the three basins of Lake Erie--eastern, central, and western--as well as for Saginaw Bay. To simplify matters, the development of an objective for only one area, western Lake Erie, will be discussed in this example.

The first consideration in developing an objective for western Lake Erie was to determine what environmental conditions are desired by the two countries for this area. To determine this, the Agreement was consulted. The general objectives discussed in the introduction to this paper include one, (e), that bears on this question. It calls for nutrient levels to be low enough to prevent interference with beneficial uses by growths of aquatic life. In another part of the Agreement, a phosphorus control program is specified to reduce present levels of algal growth in Lake Erie (the level at the time this was written exceeded 30 µg/l). Although such guidance is somewhat vague, it suggests that it is desired that the levels of algae and so phosphorus be substantially reduced from those present when the Agreement was signed and that this reduction be great enough so algal growths do not cause problems for other uses.

Thomas (1975) suggests that the green alga *Cladophora* starts to become a nuisance at about 15 µg/l, and it is only above this level that certain uses, especially for recreation and as a drinking water source, are interfered with. This was determined to be the lowest level in the literature where there is indication of interference with beneficial uses. Thus, this level was set as the objective for this area.

The Agreement contains further guidance for desired conditions in other areas of the Great Lakes, and these have been applied to develop phosphorus objectives for these areas. These objectives vary from the level recommended for western Lake Erie, but were set by basically the same procedure (Thomas et al., 1980).

References

- Andrew, R. W. 1976. Toxicity relationships to copper forms in natural waters. In: Toxicity to Biota of Metal Forms in Natural Waters, R.W. Andrew, P.V. Hodson, and D.E. Konasewich, eds. Great Lakes Research Advisory Board, International Joint Commission, Windsor, Ontario. pp. 127-143.
- Beeton, A. M. 1969. Changes in the environment and biota of the Great Lakes. In: Eutrophication: Causes, Consequences, Correctives. Nat. Acad. Sci., Washington, D.C. pp. 150-187.
- Brungs, W. A. 1969. Chronic toxicity of zinc to the fathead minnow, *Pimephales promelas* Rafinesque. Trans. Amer. Fish. Soc. 98:272-279.
- National Academy of Sciences and National Academy of Engineering. 1973. Water quality criteria 1972. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Ecol. Res. Ser., R3-73-033. 594 pp.
- Schelske, C. L. and E. F. Stoermer. 1972. Phosphorus, silica, and eutrophication of Lake Michigan. In: Nutrients and Eutrophication, G.E. Likens, ed. Amer. Soc. Limnol. Oceanog., Spec. Sym. 1:157-171.
- Spague, J. B., P. F. Elson, and R. L. Saunders. 1965. Sublethal copper-zinc pollution in a salmon river: a field and laboratory study. Air Water Poll. 9:531-543.
- Thomas, N. A., A. Robertson, and W. C. Sonzogni. 1980. Review of control objectives: new target loads and input controls. In: Phosphorus Management Strategies for Lakes, R. C. Loehr, C. S. Martin, and W. Rast, eds. Ann Arbor Science, Ann Arbor, MI. pp 61-90.
- Wong, P. T. S., Y. K. Chau, and P. L. Luxon. 1978. Toxicity of a mixture of metals on freshwater algae. J. Fish. Res. Bd. Can. 35:479-481.